

Electronic nicotine delivery systems (ENDS): A new gateway to tobacco use

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ABSTRACT. Electronic cigarettes, also known as electronic nicotine delivery systems (ENDS), have emerged over the past decade as alternatives to conventional tobacco products. Initially promoted as harm-reduction tools for adult smokers, they have rapidly gained popularity among adolescents, creating new challenges for healthcare professionals and families. ENDS are battery-powered devices that heat a liquid generally composed of nicotine, propylene glycol, vegetable glycerin, and various flavorings, producing an inhaled aerosol. The aerosol contains nicotine and other potentially toxic substances, contributing to dependence and exposing users to respiratory, cardiovascular, and systemic risks. From a public health prevention perspective, it is essential that physicians, parents, and educators understand the appeal of these devices, which is often associated with social trends and digital influences. Providing clear information, fostering open dialogue, and promoting critical thinking regarding advertising messages are key strategies to support adolescents and prevent early initiation of nicotine use. This narrative review synthesizes current evidence on the toxicological profile, usage patterns, and health risks associated with ENDS.

Keywords: *Vaping; Electronic nicotine delivery systems; Adolescents; Tobacco use disorder; Smoking prevention.*

Electronic nicotine delivery technologies encompass two main categories: electronic nicotine delivery systems (ENDS), which aerosolize a liquid solution that may contain nicotine, and heated tobacco products (HTPs), which heat processed tobacco sticks without reaching combustion.¹ From a regulatory perspective, some frameworks further distinguish between nicotine-containing and non-nicotine electronic delivery systems.

ENDS, commonly known as electronic cigarettes, have become increasingly popular over the past decade as alternatives to conventional tobacco products. Although initially promoted as harm reduction tools for adult smokers, their use has risen markedly among adolescents, creating new challenges for public health and pediatric practice. Understanding their emergence and the social context that facilitates their adoption is essential for developing effective prevention strategies aimed at avoiding early nicotine exposure in adolescents.

This narrative review synthesizes current evidence on the toxicological profile, usage patterns, and health risks associated with ENDS.

DISCUSSION

Device composition and functioning

Generalities. An electronic cigarette is a battery-powered device designed to generate an inhalable aerosol from a liquid solution. Its core components include a rechargeable battery, a power control system, a heating element (coil), a liquid reservoir, and a mouthpiece. The liquid reservoir, often referred to as a tank or clearomizer in many second-generation models, is typically a transparent chamber that stores the e-liquid. Within this unit lies the heating-coil assembly. Wicking materials, commonly made of silica, cotton, or similar fibers, extend from or surround the coil and absorb the liquid. Through capillary action, the wick continuously delivers the e-liquid to the heating element. When the user activates the device, electrical power from the battery is supplied to the coil, which rapidly increases in temperature. The e-liquid in contact with the heated surface undergoes vaporization. As this vapor travels through the central airflow channel and mixes with ambient air, it cools and condenses into an aerosol. The aerosol is then inhaled through the mouthpiece.¹ Fig. 1 provides an overview of the internal structure of an electronic cigarette and its aerosol-producing components.

Figure 1. Internal structure of an electronic cigarette and its aerosol-generating components (AI-assisted figure).

The inhaled aerosol is not water vapor but a complex mixture of particles and gases, the composition of which varies according to the formulation of the device liquid. Its major constituents include humectants such as propylene glycol and glycerin, nicotine, and flavorings. Although ENDS do not involve combustion, unlike conventional cigarettes, they nonetheless deliver nicotine, the psychoactive substance responsible for dependence, as well as other toxic compounds.²

When heated, humectants become aerosolized and carry other components transferred from the vaping liquid.³ Upon inhalation, these compounds cause irritation of the respiratory tract, which may exacerbate underlying respi-

ratory diseases and increase susceptibility to infections. In this context, electronic cigarette use has been associated with worsening of diseases such as asthma, cystic fibrosis, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD).⁴ When subjected to heating, these constituents can generate small organic molecules such as formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, and acrolein.² Some of these toxics are classified as carcinogenic.^{2,5,6} Metals including aluminum, chromium, iron, lead, manganese, nickel, and tin have also been detected,^{6,7} as well as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) such as xylene and benzene, and tobacco-specific nitrosamines.⁸ Table 1 summarizes the substances identified in vaping liquids and aerosols.^{1,6,8,9}

TABLE 1. Constituents of electronic cigarette e-liquid and aerosol (adapted from Dinakar and O'Connor).¹

	E-liquid	Aerosol
Solvents	Glycerol, propylene glycol	Glycerol, propylene glycol
Nicotine	Yes	Yes
Flavoring agents	Aldehydes, vanillin, cinnamaldehyde, among others	Aldehydes, vanillin, cinnamaldehyde, among others
Other chemicals	Acetone, acrolein, 1,3-butadiene, cyclohexane, diethylene glycol (DEG), ethylene glycol (EG), ethanol, formaldehyde	Acetaldehyde, acetone, acrolein, formaldehyde, N-nitrosornicotine (NNN), 4-(methylnitrosamino)-1-(3-pyridyl)-1-butanone (NNK), toluene
Tobacco alkaloids	Nornicotine, anabasine, myosmine	Trace amounts reported
Metals	Cadmium, lead, zinc, copper, aluminum, chromium, iron, manganese, nickel, tin	Cadmium, lead, nickel, tin, copper

The fact that many of these products are illegal makes it difficult to determine the exact composition of the liquids. As a result, the inhaled chemical profile is variable, posing challenges in terms of exposure assessment and toxicity.

Nicotine. Nicotine is the psychoactive substance responsible for dependence in both conventional cigarettes and electronic cigarettes. As with other addictive substances, the risk of dependence is greater with earlier initiation of use, particularly when regions of the cerebral cortex such as the frontal cortex have not yet completed their development. Inhalation of aerosol from a nicotine-containing electronic cigarette produces peak serum nicotine concentrations within 5 minutes.⁹ This rapid systemic delivery is similar to that achieved with conventional cigarette smoking and results in a user experience that more closely resembles smoking than nicotine replacement therapies approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA).⁴

Nicotine added to most electronic cigarette liquids is isolated from the tobacco plant, although synthetic nicotine is now also available. Tobacco-derived nicotine undergoes purification and distillation to a high degree of chemical purity; however, it is impossible to completely eliminate trace impurities, including nicotine-related alkaloids and tobacco-specific nitrosamines (TSNAs). TSNAs are well-established carcinogenic and mutagenic compounds.⁶⁻⁸ The nicotine content of cartridges and refill solutions is highly variable and marketed in multiple formulations. Analyses of electronic cigarette liquids have identified nicotine concentrations ranging from 0 to 87.2 mg/mL. Moreover, the actual nicotine content frequently does not correspond to the concentrations stated on product labels.⁸ Higher-concentration preparations (e.g., 3.6% nicotine) may contain more than 1 gram of nicotine per 30 mL bottle, thereby increasing the risk of acute poisoning in children and pets following accidental exposure or ingestion. Cases of both unintentional and intentional overdose resulting from ingestion of cartridge contents have been reported.⁹

Flavoring agents. Flavoring agents constitute another major component of electronic cigarette liquids. They are added to enhance palatability and increase product appeal, with hundreds of available varieties, including fruit, candy, menthol, beverage, and dessert flavors. These formulations substantially increase attractiveness, particularly among adolescents and young adults. Most flavoring compounds are derived from the food industry and have been evaluated for safety in the context of oral ingestion, but not for inhalational exposure. Therefore, their respiratory safety profile remains inadequately characterized.

Upon heating, certain flavoring agents may generate toxic

or irritant by-products. For example, diacetyl, used to impart a buttery or creamy flavor, has been associated with cases of bronchiolitis obliterans.¹⁰ Other compounds, including aldehydes, vanillin, and cinnamaldehyde, have been shown to induce oxidative stress, airway inflammation, and cellular injury in the respiratory epithelium.^{11,12}

The presence of flavorings in electronic cigarettes facilitates their use among adolescents, as they mask the bitter or irritant taste of nicotine, thereby promoting initiation and reinforcing dependence. Products with flavors such as cherry, grape, bubble gum, and cotton candy are clearly not intended for established adult tobacco users. Moreover, adolescents report that flavors are a primary reason for using tobacco products and tend to perceive flavored products as less harmful. One study found that more than 80% of adolescents who had ever used a tobacco product initiated use with a flavored product.¹³

Epidemiology and patterns of use

In the United States (US), the percentage of adults who used electronic cigarettes increased from 4.5% in 2019 to 6.5% in 2023. In both years, men were more prone to using electronic cigarettes than women. Young adults aged 21 to 24 showed the highest rates of use in 2023, reaching 15.5%.¹⁴

A bimodal pattern of consumption can be described: on the one hand, adult smokers who seek to quit under the mistaken belief that electronic cigarettes are appropriate smoking cessation tools; on the other hand—of particular concern—their use among adolescents and young adults, sometimes in the absence of a significant prior history of tobacco product use. This is especially worrisome given that exposure occurs during a critical developmental period in which the brain continues to mature.¹⁵

Electronic cigarettes are not approved as nicotine replacement therapy for smoking cessation. Although nicotine-containing pharmacologic preparations are available and approved for tobacco cessation, these are not delivered in electronic cigarette form. Nicotine is an addictive substance, and the use of electronic cigarettes among non-smokers carries the adverse effect of promoting nicotine dependence.⁴

The use of ENDS among adolescents has increased in recent years. According to the Seventh National Study on the Consumption of Psychoactive Substances among Secondary School Students in Argentina (2025), vaping or electronic cigarette use in the previous year ranked as the third most commonly used substance among adolescents, after energy drinks and alcohol. Overall, 29% of students reported recent vaping use.¹⁶ Appealing device designs and the addition of

flavoring agents are key factors driving early uptake. This, combined with perceptions of reduced harm, digital media influence, peer pressure, and targeted marketing strategies, contributes to their growing popularity. Understanding these usage patterns is essential for developing effective, population-specific prevention interventions tailored to adolescents.

Clinical manifestations

The use of electronic cigarettes or vaping devices has been associated with multiple clinical manifestations resulting from exposure to nicotine, solvents, flavoring agents, and other potentially toxic substances present in the inhaled aerosol, as previously described.

Respiratory complications are the most frequently reported. Chronic cough, dyspnea, and wheezing have been described, secondary to bronchial irritation and inflammation.^{17,18} Cases of bronchitis and chemical pneumonitis associated with aldehydes and other carbonyl compounds in the vapor have also been reported.¹⁹ A particularly relevant entity is acute lung injury associated with vaping or electronic devices, known as EVALI (E-cigarette or Vaping-Associated Lung Injury). This condition is characterized by dyspnea, cough, chest pain, fever, and hypoxemia, with bilateral pulmonary infiltrates on chest imaging.²⁰ It has been primarily linked to liquids containing vitamin E acetate and has been identified predominantly in individuals using products containing cannabis or tetrahydrocannabinol (THC).² In Argentina, EVALI has been a mandatorily reportable disease since 2019.² In chronic users, functional abnormalities have been observed, including reduced forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV₁) and increased airway resistance.²¹

At the cardiovascular level, vaping increases heart rate and blood pressure due to the sympathomimetic effects of nicotine.²² Endothelial dysfunction, oxidative stress, and increased platelet aggregation have been demonstrated, potentially promoting atherosclerotic processes and ischemic events. In individuals with pre-existing cardiovascular disease, these effects may exacerbate the risk of arrhythmias and coronary artery disease.²³⁻²⁵

Nicotine exposure through vaping induces dependence and withdrawal syndrome, characterized by irritability, anxiety, insomnia, and difficulty concentrating. In adolescents, its use has been associated with alterations in brain development, affecting attention, memory, and impulse control.²⁶⁻²⁹

Acute electronic cigarette use may result in headache and dizziness as manifestations of mild intoxication. Nausea, vomiting, and abdominal pain have been described, associated with gastric irritation or nicotine toxicity.²⁸ In more se-

vere cases, systemic toxicity may lead to persistent vomiting, diaphoresis, and tachycardia.²⁹

Electronic cigarette use has been associated with tooth discoloration, dental caries, periodontal disease, and oral mucosal lesions. Its aerosols may also adversely affect the oral microbiome, contributing to the development of a variety of oral disorders. In addition, electronic cigarettes can alter salivary composition and properties, including reducing its antibacterial and antioxidant capacity, which may further promote oral disease.³⁰

Thermal or chemical injuries due to device malfunction or direct contact with e-liquid have also been reported, as well as taste and smell disturbances associated with certain flavoring agents.¹² Several studies have demonstrated increased oxidative stress and systemic inflammation, with potential implications for immune function and metabolic regulation.^{31,32}

Passive exposure

Although passive exposure to smoke from conventional cigarettes carries well-established health risks, data regarding secondhand exposure to aerosols generated by electronic cigarettes remain limited. Traditional cigarettes produce smoke composed primarily of solid and semi-solid particulate matter, whereas electronic devices generate a semi-liquid aerosol.

Approximately 80% of passive exposure to conventional cigarette smoke results from sidestream smoke produced by combustion of the cigarette, whereas nearly 100% of the aerosol generated by electronic cigarettes is directly inhaled by the user, with little to no sidestream emission. Passive exposure therefore derives mainly from exhaled aerosol.⁵

The composition of ENDS aerosol varies according to the constituents of the e-liquid and the voltage applied to the vaping device. Given these differences, the health effects associated with passive exposure to electronic cigarette aerosol are not directly comparable to those of secondhand tobacco smoke.³³

Regulatory framework

Argentina. In 2011, Argentina's National Administration of Drugs, Foods, and Medical Devices (ANMAT) prohibited the importation, distribution, sale, and advertising of electronic cigarettes, their accessories, and nicotine-containing cartridges. In 2023, the Ministry of Health ratified this prohibition through Resolution 565/2023,³⁴ extending it to newer devices and so-called heated tobacco products. After a 15-year ban, in May 2026, Argentina repealed its total prohibition on e-cigarettes and established a regulatory

framework for their commercialization.³⁵ Current regulations limit sales to tobacco-flavored products and maintain the ban on disposable devices. Furthermore, restrictions on their use in enclosed public spaces remain in effect under the provisions of the National Tobacco Control Law (Law No. 26,687).

European Union (EU). Regulation of e-cigarettes in the EU is primarily based on the Tobacco Products Directive (TPD), which entered into force in 2014 and has applied across Member States since 2016. The sale of electronic cigarettes to individuals under 18 years of age is prohibited, and several countries have strengthened these restrictions or increased the minimum age.³⁶

United States (US). In the US, Tobacco 21 was enacted in December 2019, establishing 21 years as the minimum legal age to purchase tobacco products and e-cigarettes nationwide.³⁷ In 2020, the FDA implemented an enforcement policy prioritizing action against illegally marketed ENDS, specifically cartridge-based flavored products (excluding tobacco- and menthol-flavored products) and any electronic cigarettes marketed to minors or likely to promote youth use. This policy responded to a public health concern aimed at preventing flavored vaping products from facilitating nicotine initiation among adolescents.³⁸

Prevention and support

Preventive strategies targeting ENDS use among adolescents focus on educational, regulatory, and community-based

interventions. These include providing clear, evidence-based information regarding the risks of vaping, particularly within school settings and primary care; strengthening adolescents' personal and social skills to resist peer influence; limiting product availability through regulation of sales, advertising, and youth access; promoting the involvement of families and educators in early detection and supportive intervention; and implementing vape-free school policies. Combined with tailored communication campaigns directed at parents and adolescents, these measures aim to reduce initiation and ongoing use.

CONCLUSIONS

Current evidence indicates that electronic cigarettes serve as a gateway to nicotine use among adolescents and are associated with acute and chronic health effects driven by inflammatory and oxidative mechanisms, primarily involving the pulmonary and cardiovascular systems. Strengthening prevention strategies, health education efforts, and regulatory measures governing access to and commercialization of these products is therefore essential to mitigate their public health impact.

Conflicts of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

- 1 Dinakar C, O'Connor GT. The Health Effects of Electronic Cigarettes. *N Engl J Med*. 2016 Oct 6;375(14):1372-81. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmra1502466>
- 2 Salim M. Programa Nacional de Actualización Pediátrica (PRONAP). Buenos Aires: Sociedad Argentina de Pediatría; 2024. Vapeo - Cigarrillo electrónico; p. 76-85.
- 3 Li Y, Burns AE, Tran LN, Abellar KA, Poindexter M, Li X, Madl AK, Pinkerton KE, Nguyen TB. Impact of e-Liquid Composition, Coil Temperature, and Puff Topography on the Aerosol Chemistry of Electronic Cigarettes. *Chem Res Toxicol*. 2021 May 5;34(6):1640-54. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrestox.1c00070>
- 4 Dirección General de Salud Pública. Informe sobre los cigarrillos electrónicos: situación actual, evidencia disponible y regulación [Internet]. Madrid: Ministerio de Sanidad; 2022 [cited 2026 Mar 2]. 39 p. Available from: <https://www.sanidad.gob.es/areas/promocionPrevencion/tabaco/profesionales/docs/InformeCigarrilloselectronicos.pdf>
- 5 Robertson NE, Connolly J, Shevchenko N, Mascal M, Pinkerton KE, Nicklisch SC, Nguyen TB. Chemical Composition of Aerosols from the E-Cigarette Vaping of Natural and Synthetic Cannabinoids. *Chem Res Toxicol*. 2024 Nov 13. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrestox.4c00326>
- 6 Usuga David M. Efectos nocivos del cigarrillo electrónico para la salud humana. Una revisión. *Rev Colomb Neumol*. 2023 Jun 1;35(1):46-66. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.30789/rcneumologia.v35.n1.2023.604>
- 7 Cao DJ, Aldy K, Hsu S, McGetrick M, Verbeck G, De Silva I, Feng SY. Review of Health Consequences of Electronic Cigarettes and the Outbreak of Electronic Cigarette, or Vaping, Product Use-Associated Lung Injury. *J Med Toxicol*. 2020 Apr 16;16(3):295-310. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13181-020-00772-w>
- 8 Videla AJ, Casetta B. Guía de lectura rápida para el equipo de salud: Cigarrillo Electrónico [Internet]. Buenos Aires: Ministerio de Salud; 2020 [cited 2026 Mar 2]. 16 p. Available from: <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/bancos/2020-06/guia-del-lectura-rapida-cigarrillo-electronico-2020.pdf>

- 9 Hoffman RS, Gosselin S, Nelson LS, Howland MA, Lewin NA, Smith SW, Goldfrank LR, editors. Goldfrank's Clinical Manual of Toxicologic Emergencies. 2nd ed. New York: McGraw Hill; 2023. Nicotine; p. 436-9.
- 10 Kanwal R. Bronchiolitis obliterans in workers exposed to flavoring chemicals. *Curr Opin Pulm Med*. 2008 Mar;14(2):141-6. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1097/mcp.0b013e3282f52478>
- 11 Muthumalage T, Prinz M, Ansah KO, Gerloff J, Sundar IK, Rahman I. Inflammatory and Oxidative Responses Induced by Exposure to Commonly Used e-Cigarette Flavoring Chemicals and Flavored e-Liquids without Nicotine. *Front Physiol*. 2018 Jan 11;8. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2017.01130>
- 12 Clapp PW, Pawlak EA, Lackey JT, Keating JE, Reeber SL, Glish GL, Jaspers I. Flavored e-cigarette liquids and cinnamaldehyde impair respiratory innate immune cell function. *Am J Physiol Lung Cell Mol Physiol*. 2017 Aug 1;313(2):L278—L292. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajplung.00452.2016>
- 13 Ambrose BK, Day HR, Rostron B, Conway KP, Borek N, Hyland A, Villanti AC. Flavored Tobacco Product Use Among US Youth Aged 12-17 Years, 2013-2014. *JAMA*. 2015 Nov 3;314(17):1871. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2015.13802>
- 14 Vahratian A, Briones EM, Jamal A, Marynak KL. Electronic Cigarette Use Among Adults in the United States, 2019-2023. *NCHS Data Brief*. 2025 Jan;(524):CS356607. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.15620/cdc/174583>
- 15 National Institute on Drug Abuse. Preface [Internet]. Bethesda (MD): National Institute on Drug Abuse; 2020 Jul 6 [cited 2026 Mar 2]. Available from: <https://nida.nih.gov/research-topics/addiction-science/drugs-brain-behavior-science-of-addiction>
- 16 Observatorio Argentino de Drogas. Séptimo estudio nacional sobre consumo de sustancias psicoactivas en estudiantes de enseñanza secundaria. argentina, 2025. informe sobre los consumos de tabaco, marihuana y cigarrillo electrónico [Internet]. Sedronar; 2026 Apr [cited 2026 May 16]. 47 p. Available from: https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/oad-2026-septimo_estudio_nacional_sobre_el_consumo_de_sustancias psicoactivas_en_estudiantes_secundaria.pdf
- 17 Chand HS, Muthumalage T, Maziak W, Rahman I. Pulmonary Toxicity and the Pathophysiology of Electronic Cigarette, or Vaping Product, Use Associated Lung Injury. *Front Pharmacol*. 2020 Jan 14;10. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2019.01619>
- 18 Clapp PW, Jaspers I. Electronic Cigarettes: Their Constituents and Potential Links to Asthma. *Curr Allergy Asthma Rep*. 2017 Oct 5;17(11). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11882017-0747-5>
- 19 Layden JE, Ghinai I, Pray I, Kimball A, Layer M, Tenforde MW, Navon L, Hoots B, Salvatore PP, Elderbrook M, Haupt T, Kanne J, Patel MT, Saathoff-Huber L, King BA, Schier JG, Mikosz CA, Meiman J. Pulmonary Illness Related to E-Cigarette Use in Illinois and Wisconsin — Final Report. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Mar 5;382(10):903-16. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa1911614>
- 20 Vardavas CI, Anagnostopoulos N, Kougias M, Evangelopoulou V, Connolly GN, Behrakis PK. Short-term Pulmonary Effects of Using an Electronic Cigarette. *Chest*. 2012 Jun;141(6):1400-6. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.11-2443>
- 21 Benowitz NL, Fraiman JB. Cardiovascular effects of electronic cigarettes. *Nat Rev Cardiol*. 2017 Mar 23;14(8):447-56. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrcardio.2017.36>
- 22 Moheimani RS, Bhetraratana M, Yin F, Peters KM, Gornbein J, Araujo JA, Middlekauff HR. Increased Cardiac Sympathetic Activity and Oxidative Stress in Habitual Electronic Cigarette Users. *JAMA Cardiol*. 2017 Mar 1;2(3):278. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamacardio.2016.5303>
- 23 Carnevale R, Sciarretta S, Violi F, Nocella C, Loffredo L, Perri L, Peruzzi M, Marullo AG, De Falco E, Chimenti I, Valenti V, Biondi-Zoccai G, Frati G. Acute Impact of Tobacco vs Electronic Cigarette Smoking on Oxidative Stress and Vascular Function. *Chest*. 2016 Sep;150(3):606-12. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chest.2016.04.012>
- 24 Qasim H, Karim ZA, Rivera JO, Khasawneh FT, Alshbool FZ. Impact of Electronic Cigarettes on the Cardiovascular System. *J Am Heart Assoc*. 2017 Sep 22;6(9). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1161/jaha.117.006353>
- 25 Glantz SA, Bareham DW. E-Cigarettes: Use, Effects on Smoking, Risks, and Policy Implications. *Annu Rev Health*. 2018 Apr;39(1):215-35. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-publhealth-040617-013757>
- 26 Yuan M, Cross SJ, Loughlin SE, Leslie FM. Nicotine and the adolescent brain. *J Physiol*. 2015 Jun 23;593(16):3397-412. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1113/jp270492>
- 27 Breland A, Soule E, Lopez A, Ramôa C, El-Hellani A, Eissenberg T. Electronic cigarettes: what are they and what do they do? *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. 2016 Jan 15;1394(1):5-30. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.12977>
- 28 Tzortzi A, Kapetanstradaki M, Evangelopoulou V, Behrakis P. A Systematic Literature Review of E-Cigarette-Related Illness and Injury: Not Just for the Respiriologist. *Int J Environ Res Health*. 2020 Mar 27;17(7):2248. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17072248>
- 29 Wills TA, Pagano I, Williams RJ, Tam EK. E-cigarette use and respiratory disorder in an adult sample. *Drug Alcohol Depend*. 2019 Jan;194:363-70. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2018.10.004>
- 30 Cichońska D, Kusiak A, Goniewicz ML. The Impact of E-Cigarettes on Oral Health-A Narrative Review. *Dent*

- J (Basel). 2024 Dec 10;12(12):404. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/dj12120404>
- 31 Higham A, Rattray NJ, Dewhurst JA, Trivedi DK, Fowler SJ, Goodacre R, Singh D. Electronic cigarette exposure triggers neutrophil inflammatory responses. *Respir Res.* 2016 May 17;17(1). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12931-0160368-x>
- 32 Chatterjee S, Tao JQ, Johncola A, Guo W, Caporale A, Langham MC, Wehrli FW. Acute exposure to e-cigarettes causes inflammation and pulmonary endothelial oxidative stress in nonsmoking, healthy young subjects. *Am J Physiol Lung Cell Mol Physiol.* 2019 Aug 1;317(2):L155—L166. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajplung.00110.2019>
- 33 Manigrasso M, Protano C, Vitali M, Avino P. Passive Vaping from Sub-Ohm Electronic Cigarette Devices. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021 Nov 4;18(21):11606. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182111606>
- 34 Argentina. Ministerio de Salud. Resolución 565/2023 [Internet]. Boletín Oficial de la República Argentina. 2023 Mar 27. [cited 2026 May 16]. Available from: <https://www.boletinoficial.gob.ar/detalleAviso/primera/283303/20230327>
- 35 Argentina. Ministerio de Salud. Resolución 549/2026 [Internet]. Boletín Oficial de la República Argentina. 2026 May 4. [cited 2026 May 16]. Available from: <https://www.boletinoficial.gob.ar/detalleAviso/primera/341494/20260504>
- 36 European Commission. Tobacco Products Directive 2014/40/ EU [Internet]. Brussels: European Commission. 2014. [cited 2026 May 16]. Available from: https://health.ec.europa.eu/tobacco/product-regulation_en
- 37 U.S. Food and Drug Administration. (2020, January 2). Tobacco 21: Raising the Minimum Age of Sale of Tobacco Products to 21. FDA. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/tobacco-products/retail-sales-tobacco-products/tobacco-21>
- 38 U.S. Food and Drug Administration. (2020, January). Enforcement Policy on Unauthorized Flavored Cartridge-Based E-Cigarettes and Other Electronic Nicotine Delivery Systems (ENDS). FDA. Available from: <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/fda-finalizes-enforcement-policy-on-unauthorized-flavored-cartridge-based-e-cigarettes-that-appeal-to-children-including-fruit-and-mint-300980613.html>